

Reaction of β -Diketonates of Nickel(II) with Thiocyanate and Azide Ions

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β -diketonates of Nickel(II) were reacted with potassium thiocyanate and sodium azide in 1:2 molar ratio in methanol medium and complexes having the general formula $M_2[Ni(\beta\text{-dik})_2X_2]$ where $M=K^+$ or Na^+ , H $\beta\text{-dik}$ =acetylacetonate, benzoylacetonate or dibenzoyl methane and $X=SCN^-$ or N_3^- were isolated. IR study indicates that thiocyanate is coordinated to the metal ion through sulphur and the azide group through terminal nitrogen atom. The magnetic measurement and electronic spectral data reveal that complexes are octahedral. The molar conductance values indicate that the complexes are 1:2 electrolytes.

A large number of mixed ligand complexes of β -diketonates of nickel(II) with neutral heterodonor ligands have been reported¹⁻⁶. Complexes of nickel(II) containing β -diketonates and pseudohalides do not appear to have been studied earlier. Thiocyanate is an ambidentate group capable of bonding either through nitrogen or sulphur and ligand characteristics of azide group also have been well studied. It was therefore thought worthwhile to investigate the reaction of thiocyanate and azide ion with the β -diketonates of nickel(II) and to study the nature of their coordination around the central metal ion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. The β -diketonates of nickel(II) were prepared by known methods. The thiocyanate and azide complexes were obtained by refluxing either the solution or suspensions of β -diketonates of nickel(II) in methanol with methanol solution of potassium thiocyanate or sodium azide in 1:2 molar ratio for a period of two to three hours. On cooling the resulting solution, solid products separated out, which were suction filtered, washed with absolute methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Nickel and sulphur were estimated by standard methods. Electrical conductance was measured on $M/1000$ solutions either in acetone or pyridine using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature using Guoy method. The infrared absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra in solution were recorded using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. Colour, melting point, analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are given in Table-1. The infrared absorption bands pertaining

to β -diketonates, thiocyanate and azide groups and the electronic spectra are returned in Table 2.

Discussion

The compounds reported in this investigation have the general composition $M_2[Ni(\beta\text{-dik})_2X_2]$. The thiocyanato compounds of bis acetylacetonate and benzoylacetonate are fairly soluble in acetone whereas the azido compounds and the thiocyanato compound of bis dibenzoyl methane are only soluble in pyridine. The molar conductance values of the compounds in the respective solvents indicate them to be 2:1 electrolytes.

All the compounds are paramagnetic with u_{eff} values ranging between 3.00 and 3.30 BM (Table 1) which are within the range for octahedral complexes of nickel(II) (2.83-3.40 BM)⁷. These compounds are therefore, spin-free, octahedral complexes involving the use of $4s$, $4p^3$, $4d^2$ hybrid orbitals for bonding.

Infrared spectra By the introduction of an extra ligand to the structural assembly of the metal complex, the $\nu(C-C)$, $\nu(C-O)$ and $\nu(M-O)$ which are involved in a resonance system are expected to undergo shifts. In the present study, the $\nu(C-C)$ and $\nu(C-O)$ are shifted to lower frequencies as expected.

The thiocyanate group can be terminal N- or S-bonded or can function as a bridging group. The changes in $\nu(C-N)^8$ and $\nu(C-S)^9$ consequent to different modes of bonding have been discussed earlier. In the present compounds, $\nu(C-N)$ bands appear at $\sim 2030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(C-S)$ bands appear at $\sim 710\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2) indicating the presence of terminal S-bonded thiocyanate group.

The ionic KN_3 absorbs¹⁰ at 2041 cm^{-1} (assignment)

TABLE 1

ANALYTICAL, MELTING POINT, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES.

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	% Nickel Found	% Nickel Reqd.	% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Reqd.	ΛM (mhos)	μ_{eff} (BM)
K ₂ [Ni(acac) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	deep green	217 (d)	12.8	12.9	14.8	14.1	268	3.00
Na ₂ [Ni(acac) ₂ (N ₃) ₂]	light green	>250	15.2	15.0			128	3.00
K ₂ [Ni(bzac) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	pea green	>250	9.4	10.1	11.3	11.1	254	3.30
Na ₂ [Ni(bzac) ₂ (N ₃) ₂]	green	>250	11.4	11.4			122	3.30
K ₂ [Ni(bz bz) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	greenish yellow	>250	8.2	8.3	8.9	9.1	99	3.30
Na ₂ [Ni(bz bz) ₂ (N ₃) ₂]	bright green	>250	9.2	9.2			108	3.20

TABLE 2

INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES IN CM⁻¹

Compound	β-diketone ν(C-C) ν(C-O)		Thiocyanate ν(C-N) ν(C-S)		Azide ν _{asy} ν _{sym}		Electronic spectra (ν _{max}) ν ₁ ν ₂	
	KSCN			1963	749			
Na N ₃					2041	1344		
Ni(acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	1628	1558					<10,000	15,389
Ni(bzac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	1613	1555					<10,000	16,395
Ni(bz bz) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	1625	1555					<10,000	16,425
K ₂ [Ni(acac) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	1600	1520	2030	710			10,520	17,240
Na ₂ [Ni(acac) ₂ (N ₃) ₂]	1600	1525			2080	1260	10,526	17,860
K ₂ [Ni(bzac) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	1590	1512	2030	708			10,810	17,240
Na ₂ [Ni(bzac) ₂ (N ₃) ₂]	1600	1525			2045	1275	10,765	17,860
K ₂ [Ni(bz bz) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	1605	1530	2060	706			11,110	16,000
Na ₂ [Ni(bz bz) ₂ (N ₃) ₂]	1600	1540			2035	1270	10,265	18,180

and 1344 cm⁻¹ (ν_{sym}). The shifts in these two frequencies on coordination were reported and discussed earlier^{11,12}. In the compounds under report, the strong bands observed for ν_{sym} and ν_{asy} are in accordance with the earlier observations.

Electronic Spectra - For an octahedral nickel (II) complex three main bands are expected⁵, ν₁, 8000-13,000; ν₂, 14,000-19,000 and ν₃, 25,000-30,000 cm⁻¹ arising from ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}^o (F), → ³T_{1g}^o (F) and ³T_{1g}^o (P) transitions. In the present study the third band (ν₃) is obscured by the intense charge transfer bands. The bands noticed at 10,000-11,000 (ν₁) and 16,000-18,000 cm⁻¹ (ν₂) may be assigned to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}^o (F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}^o transitions. Besides, very weak bands also appear at ~11,000, ~12,000, ~13,800, ~14,810 and ~19,230 cm⁻¹ due to tetragonal distortion. Rowley and Drago¹³ have also assigned similar weak bands, to transition arising in molecules when passing from O_h to D_{4h} symmetry.

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